

WRITING ATTITUDE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 12 ACCOUNTANCY, BUSINESS AND MANAGEMENT (ABM) STUDENTS: BASIS FOR WRITING INTERVENTION PLAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17852798>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between writing attitude and academic performance among Grade 12 Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) students at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School in the City of Carmona, Cavite. A quantitative correlational research design was utilized, involving 225 respondents selected through purposive sampling. Writing attitude was measured using an adapted version of Podsen's Writing Attitude Scale, while academic performance was based on students' final grades in the Reading and Writing Skills subject during the second semester of School Year 2022–2023. Descriptive statistics, weighted mean, and Pearson product–moment correlation coefficient was employed to analyze the data. Results revealed that most students demonstrated a moderate level of writing attitude, while a majority achieved an outstanding level of academic performance. However, the findings revealed no significant relationship between writing attitude and academic performance ($r = -0.031$, $p = 0.642$). The results suggest that writing attitude alone may not be a strong predictor of academic achievement and that other factors may influence students' performance in writing-related subjects. Based on the findings, a writing intervention plan was proposed to enhance students' engagement and instructional strategies in writing classrooms. This study contributes to local literature on writing attitudes among senior high school ABM students and provides practical implications for educators in improving writing instruction.

Keywords: *writing attitude, academic performance, student performance, writing skills, writing interventions, senior high school*

INTRODUCTION

Writing is one of the fundamental skills students need to develop as it plays a critical role in achieving success in higher education and future careers. Inderawati et al. (2018) emphasize that writing serves as a means of communicating ideas through organized expression in a particular language. The ability to present ideas effectively in written form increases an individual's opportunity for employment and higher education (Kamariah et al., 2018). However, despite early exposure to writing instruction, many students experience difficulty in grammar, organization, and coherence. Learners often struggle with independent writing since they must simultaneously manage multiple aspects of language use, which may negatively affect both academic and professional outcomes. One factor that influences students' writing performance is their attitude toward writing (Wulandari et al., 2020).

Writing is essential for critical thinking, learning, and self-expression. Ideally, students should demonstrate a positive attitude toward writing as it plays a role in improving skills and reducing learning gaps. Tarrayo et al. (2022) report that universities have enriched curricula by integrating writing courses to improve students' ability to analyze ideas and communicate effectively. However, writing proficiency in English continues to be a major challenge among learners (Selvaraj, 2019). The growing complexity of writing tasks further increases students' anxiety and confusion. Several studies indicate that writing attitude is a significant factor affecting performance, as individuals with positive attitudes exert more effort when learning language skills (Inderawati et al., 2018). Agesty et al. (2021) similarly revealed that students with positive writing attitudes demonstrate higher confidence, while negative attitudes are associated with lower levels of engagement in writing activities.

The Department of Education acknowledges the need for remediation programs to address learning gaps among students (DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2012). However, addressing writing difficulties requires more than one-time intervention, especially when learners develop negative dispositions toward writing. At Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School, teachers observed that Grade 12 ABM students encounter challenges in performing writing tasks in the Reading and Writing Skills subject. Learning Outcomes Assessment results further indicate that many students struggle in writing despite the importance of this skill for academic success and future professional applications. Since ABM students are exposed to business communication, poor writing skills may undermine their participation in written communication required in organizational settings.

Although various studies have examined writing attitude and writing performance, the findings remain inconsistent. Several studies suggest a positive relationship between attitude and performance (Agesty et al., 2021; Hanane, 2015), while Novia and Saptarina (2020) reported no significant correlation. These conflicting findings highlight the necessity of investigating the relationship between writing attitude and academic performance in localized contexts, particularly among senior high school students in the Philippines. This study aimed to investigate the relationship between writing attitude and

academic performance among Grade 12 ABM students and serve as the basis for a writing intervention plan.

Research Questions

This study specifically aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the writing attitude of Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) Senior High School students?
2. How well do the ABM Senior High School students perform in writing as observed in their Reading and Writing subject?
3. Is there a significant relationship between students' writing attitudes and academic performance?
4. What action plan can be implemented to address students' negative writing attitudes and academic performance?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative correlational research design to examine the relationship between writing attitude and academic performance among Grade 12 Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) students. The study was conducted at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School in the City of Carmona, Province of Cavite during the School Year 2022–2023.

The respondents consisted of 225 Grade 12 ABM students enrolled in the Academic Track. Purposive sampling was used to select participants who had completed the Reading and Writing Skills subject during the second semester of the school year.

Data were collected using a researcher-administered questionnaire consisting of two parts. The first part measured students' writing attitudes using an adapted version of Podsén's (1997) Writing Attitude Scale, as utilized by Agesty et al. (2021). The instrument contained 20 items rated on a five-point Likert scale: (1) strongly disagree, (2) disagree, (3) neutral, (4) agree, and (5) strongly agree. These items assessed both positive and negative attitudes toward writing. The instrument had a reported reliability coefficient of 0.737 based on Cronbach's Alpha (Setyowati & Sukmawan, 2016). The second part of the questionnaire gathered data on students' academic performance based on their final grades in the Reading and Writing Skills subject. Grades were categorized as follows: Outstanding (90 and above), Very Satisfactory (85–89), Satisfactory (80–84), Fairly Satisfactory (75–79), and Did Not Meet Expectations (74 and below).

Prior to data collection, formal permission was obtained from the school administration and district authorities. Informed consent was secured from all participants and parents or guardians of students below 18 years old. The researchers ensured confidentiality and anonymity of responses, and data were used strictly for research purposes.

The collected data were tallied, organized, and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency distribution and weighted mean were used to determine students' levels of writing attitude and academic performance. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was employed to examine the relationship between writing attitude and academic performance at a 0.05 level of significance.

The scope of the study was limited to Grade 12 ABM students from one public senior high school and focused on writing attitude and academic performance in the Reading and Writing Skills subject. Academic performance was measured solely through students' final grades, which may be subject to variability in grading practices. Hence, findings may not be generalized to other populations.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings on students' writing attitudes, academic performance in Reading and Writing Skills, and the relationship between the two variables.

Table 1
Writing Attitude of the Students

	Frequency	Percent
Low	0	0
Moderate	127	56.4
High	98	43.6
Total	225	100.0

This table presents insights into the distribution of writing attitudes among the study participants. Notably, none of the individuals fall into the "Low" attitude category, suggesting a collective absence of participants expressing a low level of enthusiasm or interest in writing. The majority, comprising 56.4% of the sample, falls into the "Moderate" attitude category, indicating a prevailing middle-ground stance on writing attitudes within the study population. In contrast, a substantial portion, accounting for 43.6% of participants, falls into the "High" attitude category, signifying a notable number of students with a high level of enthusiasm or positive attitudes toward writing. This distribution paints a nuanced picture of the diverse range of writing attitudes within the studied group, providing valuable context for further exploration of factors influencing these attitudes and their potential impact on various outcomes.

Table 1.1
Positive Writing Attitude of Students towards Writing

Item No.	Indicators	Mean	Description	Verbal Interpretation
2	I have no fear of my writing being evaluated.	3.41	Agree	High
3	I look forward to writing down my ideas.	3.96	Agree	High
7	I would enjoy submitting my writing to magazines for evaluation and publication.	3.32	Neutral	Moderate
8	I like to write my ideas down.	4.02	Agree	High
9	I feel confident in my ability to express my ideas in writing.	3.52	Agree	High
10	I like to have my friends read what I have written.	3.57	Agree	High
12	People seem to enjoy what I write.	3.25	Neutral	Moderate
13	I enjoy writing	3.71	Agree	High
16	I like seeing my thoughts on paper.	3.94	Agree	High
17	Discussing my writing with others is an enjoyable experience.	3.53	Agree	High
18	It is easy for me to write good letters.	3.24	Neutral	Moderate
20	Writing is a lot of fun.	3.69	Agree	High
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN		3.60	Agree	High

Legend:

5.00 – 4.20 Strongly Agree 3.40 – 4.19 Agree 2.60 – 3.39 Neutral
1.80 – 2.59 Disagree 1.00 – 1.79 Strongly Disagree

Table 1.1 provides a detailed analysis of students' positive attitudes toward writing, presenting various indicators along with their mean scores, descriptions, and verbal interpretations. The indicators encompass a spectrum of sentiments related to students' perceptions and enjoyment of the writing process.

The mean scores, ranging from 3.24 to 4.02, indicate an overall positive trend in writing attitudes among the students. Noteworthy indicator, such as *"I like to write my ideas down,"* with mean score of 4.02 achieve highest mean score and fall within the "Agree" and "High" categories. These responses suggest a strong enthusiasm for and enjoyment of the act of writing.

While indicators, *"It is easy for me to write good letters,"* with mean score of 3.24 fall within the "Neutral" and "Moderate" categories, they still suggest a generally positive attitude toward writing. The general weighted mean, calculated across all indicators, is 3.60, placing it within the "Agree" and "High" categories. This consolidated measure reinforces the overall positive writing attitudes among the students.

Table 1.2
Negative Writing Attitude of Students towards Writing

Item No.	Indicators	Mean	Description	Verbal Interpretation
1	I avoid writing whenever possible.	2.82	Neutral	Moderate
4	I am afraid of writing when I know it might be evaluated.	3.17	Neutral	Moderate
5	My mind seems to go blank when I start writing.	3.30	Neutral	Moderate
11	I am nervous about my writing	3.40	Agree	High
14	I never seem to be able to write down my ideas clearly.	3.08	Neutral	Moderate
15	I am not a good writer.	3.28	Neutral	Moderate
19	I don't think I write as well as most people.	3.45	Agree	High
6	Expressing my ideas through writing is a waste of time.	2.16	Disagree	Low
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN		3.08	Neutral	Moderate

Legend:

5.00 – 4.20 Strongly Agree 3.40 – 4.19 Agree 2.60 – 3.39 Neutral
1.80 – 2.59 Disagree 1.00 – 1.79 Strongly Disagree

Table 1.2 provides an overview of students' negative attitudes toward writing, offering various indicators with their mean scores, descriptions, and verbal interpretations. These indicators span a spectrum of sentiments related to reluctance, anxiety, or challenges associated with the act of writing.

The mean scores, ranging from 2.16 to 3.45, suggest a predominantly moderate level of negative attitudes among the students. Particularly notable indicators, such as *"Expressing my ideas through writing is a waste of time"* and *"I avoid writing whenever possible,"* fall within the "Disagree" and "Low" categories, indicating a strong disagreement with the idea that writing is a waste of time and a low level of avoidance, respectively.

However, the majority of indicators, including statements like *"I am nervous about my writing," "I am afraid of writing when I know it might be evaluated,"* and *"I don't think I write as well as most people,"* fall within the "Neutral" and "Moderate" categories. These responses suggest a middle-ground attitude, indicating a degree of hesitation, nervousness, or perceived difficulty associated with certain aspects of the writing process.

The general weighted mean, calculated across all indicators, is 3.08, placing it within the "Neutral" and "Moderate" categories. This consolidated measure suggests an overall moderate level of negative attitudes toward writing among the students.

The legend provides a helpful guide for interpreting the verbal categories corresponding to the mean scores, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree." In summary, Table 1.2 presents a nuanced picture of students' negative attitudes toward writing, emphasizing both areas of disagreement and moderate concerns or challenges associated with the writing process.

Table 2
Final Grade in Reading and Writing Skill Subject of Students

	Frequency	Percent
Did not meet expectation	0	0
Fairly Satisfactory	0	0
Satisfactory	0	0
Very Satisfactory	63	28.0
Outstanding	162	72.0
Total	225	100.0

Legend:

Outstanding (5) = 90-above

Satisfactory (3) = 80-84

Did not meet expectation (1) = 74-below

Very Satisfactory (4) = 85-89

Fairly Satisfactory (2) = 75-79

Table 2 presents the distribution of final grades in Reading and Writing Skills among Grade 12 ABM students. Remarkably, there are no participants falling into the "Did not meet expectation," "Fairly Satisfactory," or "Satisfactory" categories, signifying a total absence of individuals achieving at the lower levels in these skills. On the contrary, an impressive 72.0% of participants achieved an "Outstanding" grade, indicating a high level of proficiency in Reading and Writing Skills. Furthermore, 28.0% of students achieved a "Very Satisfactory" grade, reflecting a notable proficiency in these skills. The majority of this group demonstrates outstanding reading and writing abilities, reaching the top performance standards. The lack of lower achievement categories indicates a remarkably positive academic environment among the study participants, which calls for further investigation into the factors that enable such high levels of success in reading and writing skills.

Table 3
Significant Relationship Between Writing Attitudes and Academic Performance in Reading and Writing Skills Subject

		Writing Attitudes	Final Grade in Reading and Writing Skills	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Writing Attitudes	Pearson Correlation	1	-.031		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.642	Accept H _o	No Significant
	N	225	225		
Final Grade in Reading and Writing Skills	Pearson Correlation	-.031	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.642		Accept H _o	No Significant
	N	225	225		

Table 3 provides insights into the correlation between students' writing attitudes and their academic performance in Reading and Writing Skills. The Pearson Correlation coefficient of -0.031 indicates a very weak, almost negligible, negative relationship between these two variables. Additionally, the associated p-values for both correlations are notably high at 0.642, exceeding the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. This lack of statistical significance suggests that there is no substantial or meaningful association between students' writing attitudes and their final grades in Reading and Writing Skills within the confines of this study. The decision to accept the null hypothesis further emphasizes the absence of a significant correlation. This result implies that factors beyond writing attitudes may have a more pronounced influence on academic performance in reading and writing skills among the participants. Further investigation into these factors is warranted to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics influencing academic outcomes in these specific areas.

However, this result contradicts the findings of Novia and Saptarina (2013) in their study "Process Writing Approach (PWA): the Correlation between Students' Attitude and Writing Achievement" showing the direct correlation between writing attitude and achievement.

Table 4
Action Plan on the Enhancement of Negative Writing Attitudes of Students

Key Result Areas	Time Frame	Objectives	Strategies/ Program Activities
<p>A. Teacher Development</p> <p>Subject Knowledge</p> <p>Pedagogical Competence</p>	December 2023	<p>To exhibit expertise in teaching various writing genres, including essays, narratives, reports, and creative writing, to cater to diverse writing skill requirements.</p> <p>To apply writing pedagogy, encompassing theories, methodologies, and best practices in teaching writing skills.</p>	<p>Collaborate with peers through peer observation to benchmark and adapt best practices in teaching writing</p> <p>Hold LAC session to showcase teachers' lesson plans crafted for instructing distinct writing genres. This may encompass information on teaching methods, resources, and assessment strategies</p>
<p>B. Competencies in Writing Development</p> <p>Writing Ideas Clearly</p> <p>Writing coherently</p>	February- June 2023	<p>Implement the Procedure-based Gradual Writing program to break down the writing process into smaller, manageable steps. This approach allows students to practice and develop strong writing skills</p>	<p>Introduce sequential writing skills through activities that start with sentence construction before progressing to paragraph and essay writing.</p> <p>Utilize the modeling strategy to furnish students with clear writing, offering examples of well-constructed and concise</p>

		<p>sentences or paragraphs. Breaking down how sentences are constructed and how ideas are logically organized can assist students in expressing their thoughts in a clear and understandable manner.</p> <p>Apply guided practice by providing activity templates, sentence starters, or graphic organizers to scaffold the writing process, achieving a clear progression of ideas from the introduction to the conclusion.</p> <p>Constant writing activities that gradually increase the complexity of writing tasks as students demonstrate proficiency, moving from simple sentences to compound and complex sentences, and from short paragraphs to longer compositions</p>
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<p>C. Students Attitude Development</p> <p>Value Writing as an Expression of ideas</p> <p>Seek opportunities to engage in writing and enjoy expressing thoughts on various topics.</p> <p>Working continuously to improve ability to express ideas clearly through writing</p>	<p>February – June 2023</p>	<p>Create a supportive and appreciative environment for students to cultivate a positive writing attitude</p>	<p>Highlight the diverse applications of writing in real-world situations by showcasing examples that illustrate the significance of effective writing in professional environments, journalism, social media, and personal communication.</p> <p>Design writing exercises that connect to students' individual interests and academic strand, incorporating their personal experiences, thoughts, and opinions on timely issues such as AI as an emerging technology. This approach will motivate them to see writing as a medium for expressing themselves</p> <p>Showcasing clear writing by modeling how to express ideas in a coherent manner, sharing one's own writing, and highlighting the process of</p>
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			<p>revision and refinement to improve clarity will create positive encouragement that can boost students' confidence and contribute to an overall positive writing attitude</p> <p>Accomplishing in low-pressure writing activities, such as journaling or informal reflections, that establishes a comfortable environment for self-expression, free from the constraints of formal assignments.</p>
D. Positive Writing Environment	February – June 2023	Promote positive and enriching learning environment that nurtures creativity, expression, and mutual respect among students, fostering enthusiasm for the development of writing skills.	<p>Encourage Weekly self-classroom expression Activities and integrate technology such as grammar-checking software, to enhance the writing experience of students</p> <p>Monday <i>Free-Verse Writing Day-</i> In designated time</p>

		<p>frame students will engage in uninterrupted writing, free from concerns about grammar or structure. This practice facilitates the inhibitions towards writing and will release students' creative thoughts and ideas.</p> <p>Tuesday <i>Personal Bucket List-</i> write about their aspirations and experiences they hope to achieve after exit in Senior high School</p> <p>Wednesday <i>Trek Tales-</i> Write travel diaries, whether imaginary or real, and explore diverse cultures and settings through the art of writing</p> <p>Thursday <i>Happiness Notebook-</i> Students will write about things they are thankful for each day. This could help promote students' positive classroom atmosphere</p>
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DISCUSSION

The results revealed that the majority of Grade 12 ABM students demonstrated a moderate level of writing attitude, while a substantial portion showed high writing attitudes. This finding indicates that most students neither strongly favor nor strongly resist writing activities but rather occupy a middle-ground perspective. This result is consistent with the findings of Agesty et al. (2021) and Setyowati and Sukmawan (2016), who also reported moderate levels of writing attitude among EFL learners. The students' generally positive responses to items such as enjoyment in writing, confidence in expressing ideas, and liking to see their thoughts on paper suggest that many learners appreciate writing but may still experience uncertainty or difficulty when completing writing tasks.

In terms of academic performance, the findings showed that most students achieved outstanding or very satisfactory grades in Reading and Writing Skills. This result suggests that the respondents demonstrated a high level of academic proficiency in writing-related tasks. The absence of low-performing students indicates a relatively strong instructional environment and effective classroom strategies. Tutto and Ramos (2021) reported that structured instructional approaches and curriculum alignment contributed to improved reading and writing performance among senior high school learners. Likewise, the strong performance of ABM students in this study may be attributed to regular writing exposure in their academic subjects and targeted instructional practices.

Despite students achieving high academic performance, the correlational analysis revealed no significant relationship between writing attitude and academic performance. This implies that having a positive or moderate writing attitude does not necessarily result in higher academic achievement in writing-related subjects. This finding supports the results of Novia and Saptarina (2020), who concluded that writing attitude alone does not significantly determine writing achievement. Their study emphasized that other variables such as self-confidence, writing anxiety, learning experiences, and instructional support might play a more substantial role in influencing student outcomes.

The lack of significant correlation also suggests that while attitude contributes to motivation and engagement, it may not directly translate into performance when students are evaluated through standardized grading systems. Writing performance may also be influenced by cognitive abilities, teacher assessment criteria, and academic support systems. Defazio et al. (2010) note that writing is affected by a combination of cognitive and instructional factors, reinforcing the view that attitude is only one of several components influencing academic success.

These findings therefore suggest that interventions should not focus solely on improving writing attitude but should also address writing instruction, feedback, and students' skill development. While fostering positive attitudes is valuable, ensuring consistent exposure to structured writing activities, modeling, and guided practice is equally essential.

Conclusions

The findings of the study indicate that Grade 12 ABM students generally exhibit a moderate level of writing attitude, reflecting a balanced perception toward writing wherein students experience both positive engagement and certain difficulties in the writing process.

In terms of academic performance, the students demonstrated a high level of proficiency in the Reading and Writing Skills subject, as the majority attained outstanding and very satisfactory grades.

Despite this strong academic performance, the results revealed no significant relationship between writing attitude and academic performance. This suggests that students' attitudes toward writing do not directly determine their achievement in writing-related subjects.

These findings imply that while writing attitude influences students' engagement, other factors such as instructional strategies, assessment practices, and cognitive skills may have a stronger impact on academic outcomes. Therefore, efforts to improve writing performance should extend beyond attitude enhancement and focus on strengthening teaching methodologies and skill development to support students' overall academic success.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that teachers continue to cultivate a supportive writing environment that promotes confidence and engagement in writing activities. Emphasis should be placed on encouraging students to express their ideas freely while providing constructive feedback that reinforces improvement rather than focusing solely on errors. Establishing a classroom culture that values writing as a form of communication and self-expression may help enhance students' motivation and willingness to participate in writing tasks.

Teachers are encouraged to implement structured writing strategies such as gradual skill-building, guided writing activities, and modeling of effective writing techniques. Breaking down the writing process into manageable stages, such as sentence construction, paragraph development, and full composition writing, may help students gain confidence and improve clarity in expressing ideas. Providing templates, graphic organizers, and guided prompts may further support learners as they develop writing competence.

It is also recommended that writing activities be tailored to students' academic strand and personal interests, particularly in the ABM context. Integrating real-world applications of writing, such as business correspondence, reports, and professional communication tasks, may increase students' appreciation of writing relevance and

practicality. Connecting writing lessons to authentic business situations may strengthen engagement and deepen learning.

School administrators and subject group heads are advised to support continuous professional development for writing teachers. Training programs focused on writing pedagogy, assessment methods, and instructional innovations can further strengthen teachers' capacity to deliver effective writing instruction. Collaboration through learning action cells (LAC) and peer mentoring may also foster the sharing of best practices in teaching writing.

Finally, future researchers are encouraged to examine additional variables that may influence writing performance, such as writing anxiety, motivation, self-efficacy, and instructional quality. Further studies using different research designs, larger samples, or mixed methods approaches are recommended to gain deeper insights into the factors affecting writing achievement among senior high school students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured that ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the conduct of this study. Permission to conduct the research was obtained from appropriate school authorities prior to data collection. Informed consent was secured from all respondents and parental consent from parents or guardians of participants who were below 18 years old. Participation in the study was voluntary, and respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity of participants were maintained throughout the study, and all information was handled in accordance with Republic Act No. 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The data collected were used solely for research purposes and were not disclosed to unauthorized parties. The researchers declare that there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study, that the findings were reported truthfully without bias, and that plagiarism was strictly avoided in the preparation of the manuscript. No personal identifiers were collected, and all results were used purely for academic and research purposes. Artificial intelligence tools were used solely for literature search assistance, language editing, content organization, and procedural guidance for data analysis; the authors retained full responsibility for the integrity, originality, and interpretation of the content.

Acknowledgments

This study, *Writing Attitude and Academic Performance of Grade 12 Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) Students: Basis for Writing Intervention Plan*, was successfully completed with the assistance and cooperation of various individuals and institutions who contributed to its successful implementation.

The researchers would like to express their sincere appreciation to Mrs. Laarni S. Doliente, School Head of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School (ALLSHS), and the school administrators for granting permission to conduct the study and for their valuable support during the data collection process. Gratitude is also extended to the subject teachers for

their cooperation and assistance, which contributed to the successful completion of the research.

Special recognition is given to the individuals who provided statistical guidance and technical support, whose expertise contributed to the accuracy and reliability of the data analysis. Appreciation is likewise extended to Grade 12 ABM students as respondents and their parents or guardians for their cooperation and willingness to participate in this study.

This study reflects the collective efforts and shared commitment to improving writing instruction and academic success. The researchers sincerely thank all individuals and institutions who contributed to the successful completion of this study.

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